

Mantle Anisotropy and Asthenospheric Flow Around Cratons in Southeastern South America

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Abstract

Upper mantle seismic anisotropy is one of the most important means to study dynamics of the Earth's interior. It has been extensively used to infer past and present mantle dynamics and continental evolution. Seismic anisotropy in the upper mantle can be measured by the method of shear wave splitting (SWS) of core refracted phases, such as SKS. Previous studies of SWS in South America concentrated mainly along the Andes and in southeast Brazil. Now we add extra measurements in the area of the Pantanal and Paraná basins, as part of the FAPESP "3-Basins" thematic project. With the splitting results of 47 new stations, we have a more complete and robust anisotropy map of the South America stable platform. On average, over most of the mid plate continent, the fast polarizations have an average E-W orientation, which is close to the absolute plate motion given by the hotspot reference model HS3-NUVEL-1A (median deviation of 20°). However, recent models of subduction induced mantle flow beneath South America provide a better explanation for the fast orientations (median deviation of 10°). Nevertheless, detailed analyses of the fast orientations indicate an additional component of mantle flow deviating from the cratonic blocks, at the São Francisco and Amazon cratons, and beneath the Paraná basin (called Paranapanema block). Large delay times may indicate a strong asthenospheric channel, a more coherent flow, or a thicker asthenosphere, between the Paranapanema block and the Amazon craton. Similarly, small delay times may indicate thinner anisotropic asthenosphere beneath the Paranapanema block.

Keywords: Anisotropy, Shear Wave Splitting, Asthenospheric Flow

1. Introduction

The study of seismic anisotropy beneath continents, particularly in stable areas, yields important constraints on past and present tectonic processes, and helps understanding patterns of sub-lithospheric mantle flow, in a way that cannot be achieved by other geophysical methods. Shear wave splitting is now a standard method for studying seismic anisotropy in the upper mantle, consisting of local measurements at individual stations. The resulting splitting parameters are usually interpreted as due to preferred mineral alignment, which could reflect mantle flow directions related to present-day plate motions and/or "fossil" deformation preserved in the lithospheric mantle since the last major orogeny.

Seismic anisotropy is the dependence of wave speed on the direction of seismic polarization and wave propagation. A shear wave propagating through an anisotropic medium is split into two orthogonal quasi-shear waves, one traveling faster than the other [1]. The polarization orientation of the fast component is usually named fast polarization orientation (ϕ) of anisotropy. The two waves travel at different speeds; therefore, a delay time (δt) is observed between the "fast" and "slow" components when they arrive at the station. The amount of delay time depends on the thickness of the anisotropic layer and/or the strength of anisotropy. When there is a delay time between the fast and slow components of core refracted phases, such as SKS, SKKS and PKS phases (here nominated XKS), they will exhibit some energy on the tangential component producing an elliptical particle motion. Analyses of the fast polarization orientation (ϕ) and delay time (δt) provide simple measurements that characterize seismic anisotropy directly beneath the receiving seismic station.

Fast polarization directions measured by shear wave splitting (SWS) are related to lattice preferred orientation (LPO) of anisotropic minerals (especially olivine), caused by shear deformation in the mantle [1]. Studies of mantle xenoliths show that anisotropy can be as high as 7 % [2]. Deformation through dislocation creep (crystalline dislocations within grains) is needed to cause preferred mineral orientation, and it occurs with high stress, large grain size, or both [3].

The origin of seismic anisotropy in continental areas as measured by SWS has been a big debate. Some authors such as Silver and Chan [4] and Silver [1] argued that the fast polarization orientation in stable continents correlate better with tectonic structures in the crust, implying that "frozen" anisotropy

38 imprinted by past lithospheric deformation is the main source of anisotropy.
39 Asthenospheric flow is also believed to cause mantle preferred orientation of
40 olivine [5], [6]. A common interpretation is that shear deformation due to
41 relative motion of the lithosphere with respect to the asthenosphere orients
42 the olivine a-axis and therefore causes the fast directions, ϕ to be oriented
43 parallel to the plate motion. Other models suggest that olivine LPO could be
44 induced by larger-scale flow in the asthenosphere. The fast direction would
45 coincide with the direction of flow but might differ from the direction of
46 plate motion if the plate is decoupled from the flow beneath it. Some studies
47 show contribution from lithosphere thickness variation, inducing flow around
48 cratonic roots [6], [7], [8].

49 Initial studies in SWS in Southeast Brazil indicated strong correlation of
50 fast orientations with geological trends [9], [10]. However, later studies in
51 a larger region ([7],[11]) tended to favor upper mantle flow around cratonic
52 roots, with fossil anisotropy restricted to few localized areas. Here we ex-
53 panded the shear wave splitting measurements further to the west with newly
54 installed stations (Figure 1), to have a more complete regional pattern.

55 Our results reveal that the São Francisco and Amazon cratons, and an
56 anomalous high velocity block in the Paraná basin, interpreted as a cratonic
57 nucleus [12], modulate the anisotropy orientation by diverting mantle flow.

58 2. Geological Setting

59 2.1. Paraná Basin

60 The Paraná basin of southern Brazil (Figure 1 - contour in red) is a typical
61 Paleozoic intracratonic basin and hosts one of the largest igneous provinces
62 of the world [13]. The central and northern parts of the basin have been
63 studied by passive seismology in the past 20 years, but little is known of
64 the upper mantle structure in the west of the basin, especially in Paraguay,
65 NE Argentina, and beneath the Chaco Basin. In some areas, the lithosphere
66 could be up to 200 km thick, as revealed by the compilation of Steinberger
67 and Becker [14]. Julià et al. [13] used receiver function and Rayleigh-wave
68 dispersion to confirm previous theories, that the basin sediments are under-
69 lain by a predominantly cratonic nucleus [12],[15], and mafic underplating
70 only occurred under selected sites, possibly channeled between fragmented
71 cratonic roots as seen in the model of Milani and Ramos [16].

72 Previous measurements of SWS in this area are scarce [11], and show
73 a trend of small delays with a general E-W fast direction, which has been

74 mainly correlated with the absolute plate motion directions HS3-NUVEL-1A
75 [17].

76 *2.2. Pantanal Basin*

77 The Pantanal basin (Figure 1 - Pt) is a shallow ($\sim 400\text{m}$), Quaternary
78 basin between the deep intracratonic Paraná basin and the sub-Andean
79 basins [18]. Both regional [19] and global [20] tomography models show a
80 strong S-wave low-velocity anomaly in the upper mantle (100-300 km depth)
81 beneath the Basin and continuing to the NE in the Tocantins Province, con-
82 centrated at the basin and continuing to the NE in the Tocantins Province.
83 Ussami et al. [21] proposed that the formation and subsidence of the basin
84 resulted from extensional flexural stresses due to the Andean load, in a mi-
85 grating foreland bulge. However, seismicity in the Pantanal basin is charac-
86 terized by shallow, reverse faulting events [22], which makes subsidence due
87 to flexural extension unlikely. Studies of SWS may help better understand
88 the upper mantle dynamics in this area and contribute to shed light on the
89 formation mechanism of this Quaternary Basin.

90 Again, previous measurements [11] in this area have poor coverage, due to
91 a lack of stations. Assumpção et al. [11] analyzed stations AQDB and PP1B,
92 as they were the only ones in the area at the time and have shown a deviation
93 from the proposed APM model, apparently surrounding the positive S-wave
94 anomaly in the Paraná basin.

Figure 1: Stations with the new and old measurements of SWS in southeastern South America (shown in black and white fill). The colored contours show the main geological provinces here discussed. Labels on the map are: SFC - São Francisco craton; CP - Chaco-Paraná basin (western part of the basin); Pr - Paraná basin (eastern part of the basin), Pt - Pantanal basin; TP - Tocantins province; RB - Ribeira foldbelt; AC - Amazon craton. The yellow arrow is the absolute plate motion direction HS3-NUVEL-1A.

95 3. Data and Method

96 A 3-year experiment (called “3-Basins” experiment, for short) deployed
97 35 temporary stations, with an average station spacing of 400 km, to study
98 the crust and upper mantle structure beneath the Pantanal, Paraná and
99 Chaco-Paraná Basins (Figure 1). Here we show the first SWS results from
100 this experiment together with data from the permanent Brazilian Seismo-
101 graphic Network (RSBR), analyzed between January 2011 and May 2017
102 (Table S1). We examined core refracted phases (XKS), with distances $\geq 85^\circ$
103 and magnitude ≥ 5.6 . For earthquakes deeper than 100 km, this magnitude
104 is the limit to the acceptable signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). Events with poor
105 SNR (< 2) were discarded. Seismograms were bandpass filtered between 0.03
106 and 0.3 Hz, with the exception of stations with low SNR and stations that
107 showed evidences of complex anisotropy, where the bandpass was adapted.

108 To determine the two anisotropy parameters: fast-polarization orientation
109 (ϕ) and delay time (δt) we used a Matlab based software: the SplitRacer
110 package [23]. Shear wave splitting (SWS) is analyzed based on the energy
111 minimization method of Silver and Chan [4]. To apply this method, we must
112 know the initial polarization of the wave, which is always assumed for core-
113 phases to correspond to the station backazimuth. After manual selection
114 of the events, a misalignment check is performed, based on the difference
115 between the orientation of the ellipse drawn by the XKS particle motion and
116 the back-azimuth. The results matched the misalignment measured with
117 P-wave particle motions. A correction was then applied to the misaligned
118 stations.

119 Figure 2 shows an example of splitting analysis for an event recorded at
120 station ITAB. The SplitRacer software uses the energy minimization method,
121 where a grid search for the splitting parameters (ϕ) and (δt) is carried
122 out to minimize the energy on the transverse component, after removing
123 the anisotropy effect. This is done within a time window initially chosen
124 around the phase and is repeated for 50 random variations (Figure 2-a,b).
125 The results for each time window are then plotted in histograms (Figure 2-
126 c), which are used to calculate mean splitting parameters and to check the
127 consistency of the results. Errors are calculated with 95 % confidence levels
128 from the F-test as in Silver and Chan [4] (Figure 2-f,g). Based on clear phase
129 arrivals, particle motion plots, histogram distribution, error and percentage
130 of transverse energy reduction, we classify the results as good, average, poor
131 or null.

132 After application of the inverse splitting operator on the XKS phase,
133 the elliptical particle motion should become linear (Figure 2-e), and the his-
134 togram should show one clear peak for each parameter. If the anisotropy
135 correction does not lead to linearization of the particle motion, the event is
136 classified as poor and not used in the analyses. When the wave arrives at the
137 anisotropic layer with polarization perpendicular or parallel to the fast-axis
138 direction, the wave is not split, and thus, arrives without transverse energy.
139 These measurements are called nulls, and they can also represent complex
140 anisotropic structures as discussed by Bastow et al. [24]. When there is a
141 clear phase arrival, but no energy on the transverse component and both
142 the particle motions from before and after the inversion are linear, the event
143 is classified as null. The energy grid shows 95% confidence levels usually
144 along the whole delay-time axis, at two narrow values of fast orientations,
145 corresponding to the back-azimuth and its perpendicular direction.

146 Single measurements at one station are investigated for azimuthal de-
147 pendency (Figure 3-a,b,c). For example, for a two-layer case with different
148 anisotropic properties, the splitting parameters will show a $\frac{\pi}{2}$ periodicity as
149 a function of back azimuth [3]. If azimuthal variations are not significant, a
150 single layer of anisotropy is assumed. When this is the case, we apply a joint
151 splitting analysis consisting of using all waveforms at a given station, and
152 simultaneously minimizing the transverse energy on all of them, resulting in
153 a more robust pair of splitting parameters (Figure 3-d,e,f). The corrected
154 transverse components are concatenated so that the sum of the energy on
155 all transverse components is used in the grid search for the splitting param-
156 eters. This approach significantly reduces the influence of noise and increases
157 the robustness of the splitting results, avoiding over-interpretation of single-
158 phase results [23]. The application of the inverse splitting parameters should
159 lead to a linearization of the particle motions of all waveforms, and then a
160 single layer of anisotropy explains the observations. Nevertheless, it is pos-
161 sible that due to a poor distribution of back-azimuths, a two-layer case or
162 other anisotropic complexities exist, but are not detected.

Figure 2: Analyses of a SKS phase at the station ITAB from the RSBR. a) Normalized original North and East components. b) Normalized radial and transverse components. The purple bars are 50 randomly selected time windows. c) Histograms of fast axis (ϕ) and delay time results from the 50 different time windows. d) Original particle motion. The purple bar is the back-azimuth. e) Particle motion after correction. f) Energy grid of the corrected transverse component. The black contour level refers to the 95 % confidence level. The blue cross marks the pair of splitting parameters which best minimizes the energy on the transverse component. g) Results of the splitting parameters with errors, and the energy reduction rate.

Figure 3: Compilation of all the events analyzed at station PP1B. a) Pie charts showing distribution of phases used and classification of the events. b) Polarization of fast-direction measurements plotted against back-azimuth. The black line represents the mean value, written at the top of the graph. c) Delay times and their respective back-azimuths. d) Histogram of the joint-inversion of all events of this station. e) Energy map of the joint-inversion. f) Results given by the joint-inversion.

163 4. Results and Discussion

164 The 47 new SWS measurements from both temporary and permanent
165 stations are presented on Table S1 and shown in Figure 4, together with
166 previous compilations for the stable part of South America [7], [11]. The gap
167 in XKS measurements between the Andes and SE Brazil is now partly filled,
168 and we provide a more complete and robust anisotropy map of the South
169 America stable platform. A general trend can be recognized, where most fast
170 orientations tend to be oriented E-W, roughly parallel to the absolute plate
171 motion in the hot-spot reference frame (HS3-NUVEL1A model by Gripp and
172 Gordon [17]). However, regional variations can be observed: ESE-WNW
173 orientations and small delays just south of the Amazon craton, large delays
174 and mostly ENE-WSW orientations at the Pantanal basin, small delays and
175 E-W fast orientations in the northern part of the Paraná Basin, and ESE-
176 WNW in the southern part of the Paraná basin.

177 We now discuss possible relations between the fast orientation with a
178 thick lithospheric block beneath the northern part of the Paraná basin. The
179 positive and negative S-wave anomalies derived from the surface-wave to-
180 mography, shown in Figure 4, [20] are a qualitative indication of the depth
181 of the lithosphere. As we wish to check if variations in the lithospheric thick-
182 ness are influencing the flow directions in the asthenosphere, we compare
183 our results with the tomography anomalies at 150 km depth and with the
184 lithosphere-asthenosphere boundary at a few stations obtained with S-wave
185 receiver function [25]. We find that the thickest lithosphere (160 km) at
186 station BDFB corresponds to +6% S-wave anomaly at 150 km depth. The
187 thin part of the lithosphere (≤ 80 km at CPUP) is associated with a S-wave
188 anomaly value of only 1%. In the Paraná Basin, a stack of 10 temporary
189 stations showed an average lithosphere-asthenosphere boundary of 120 km
190 depth, which is consistent with about 5% S-wave anomalies. This means that
191 the S-wave velocity anomaly at 150 km depth can be used as a rough proxy
192 for the lithospheric thickness. We have three separate main deep lithospheric
193 roots: one at the southern part of the Amazon craton, one at the São Fran-
194 cisco craton, and the Paraná basin. The positive anomaly in the tomography
195 in the Paraná basin corresponds to the cratonic block defined by Cordani [15],
196 based on radiometric dates and geological evidences. Mantovani et al. [12]
197 used gravity data to delimit this cratonic block, calling it Paranapanema
198 block (Figure 4-in dashed pink).

199 Although effects of frozen anisotropy in the lithospheric mantle had been

Figure 4: XKS fast directions from this paper (Table 1, stations SM1) and other published results. The bar lengths indicate delay time and good/average qualities of SWS are indicated by thick and thin bars. Colors indicate S-wave velocity anomalies at 150 km depth from the surface-wave tomography model SL2013 [20]. The white arrow indicate the absolute plate motion in the hotspot reference frame HS3-NUVEL1A [17]. Colored contours are the major provinces boundaries. Null bars (as brown bars) are plotted at stations where few or no measurements were found. Bold numbers denote lithosphere/asthenosphere depth from S-wave receiver functions [25].

200 suggested in some parts of SE Brazil [9], [10], [11], we note that the fast
 201 polarization orientations do not correlate with the main geological trends,
 202 with the exception of few measurements at the Ribeira belt, south of the São
 203 Francisco craton (SFC). In addition, a recent study of crustal structure with

204 gravity and geological data by Dragone et al. [26], proposed a N-S trending
205 suture zone between the Pantanal and Paraná basins (from 15°S to 30°S),
206 which is orthogonal to most observed fast orientations. Therefore, we con-
207 sider that frozen anisotropy plays a minor role in the observed SWS, and the
208 main contribution to the fast polarization orientations comes from astheno-
209 spheric flow and flow modulation due to lithosphere thickness variation at
210 cratonic keels, especially around the SFC [7] and the Amazon cratons [11].
211 Furthermore, we have evidence of flow surrounding the Parapanema block
212 in the Paraná basin, as will be shown below.

213 *4.1. Comparison with Mantle Flow*

214 The SKS splitting observed at the surface is the compound effect of the
215 passage of the shear wave through a complex series of anisotropic layers in the
216 upper mantle. Comparing the fast orientation with any single parameter can
217 be an over-simplification of heterogeneous and complex structure. However,
218 it is useful to compare the fast orientations with some simple proxies for the
219 anisotropy effect in an attempt to get insight into the main contribution to
220 the observed shear wave splitting.

221 In this section we compare our SWS results with three different proxies
222 of anisotropy: absolute plate motion with respect to the deep mantle (hot
223 spot reference frame NUVEL1A-HS3), convection velocity and LPO at 200
224 km depth from the model of Hu et al. [27]. This model calculates the up-
225 per mantle flow driven by the evolution of the Nazca plate subduction since
226 the Mid-Cretaceous. Conrad et al. [28], Assumpção et al. [11] and Miller
227 and Becker [29] had already compared their results with mantle flow mod-
228 els. However, these studies only utilized instantaneous mantle flow models.
229 Time-dependent flow is needed to better predict seismic anisotropy, due to
230 the long term response of anisotropic minerals to the cumulative strain [30].
231 The recent convection model of Hu et al. [27] depends on the subduction his-
232 tory and slab geometry and should better represent the real Earth, compared
233 to models based on tomography images or parameterized slab geometry [27].
234 Figure 5 shows the present velocity directions and the computed strain in-
235 duced LPO orientations, both at 200 km depth, compared with the observed
236 SWS results (pink and purple bars). This model considers that the conti-
237 nent has a constant thickness of 100 km and only includes a variation of
238 lithospheric depth for the Amazon craton, with a thickness of 250 km.

239 We compare the APM, model velocity and LPO directions with the SWS
240 results in the histograms of Figure 6. The median misfit values are 20.5°,

241 10.4° and 10.6° respectively. This clearly shows that the slab-induced mantle
242 flow model is a significant improvement in explaining SWS, compared with
243 the simplistic APM. Our measurements also agree with mantle flow around
244 the Amazon craton, as predicted by the model of [27], as seen in Figure 4.
245 Further south, however, especially in the Pantanal Basin, the observed SWS
246 fast orientations tend to be ENE-WSW, deviating from the general ESE-
247 WNW predicted orientations in Figure 5. We propose that the observed
248 ENE-WSW orientation may be due to flow surrounding the Paranapanema
249 block.

250 In order to visualize the deviation of the fast orientations from the Parana-
251 panema block, we calculate the difference between the LPO model directions
252 and our results. Values within a $\pm 10^\circ$ difference are taken as in good agree-
253 ment with the proposed model and are plotted in gray in Figure 7. The
254 measurements with a difference higher than 10° clockwise, are plotted in red
255 and the measurements with a difference more than 10° anticlockwise are plot-
256 ted in blue. South of the Paraná deep lithospheric block the fast orientation
257 tend to deviate away (clockwise) from it. To the northwest, especially in
258 the Pantanal basin, the fast orientations deviate anticlockwise, with respect
259 with the model of [27]. We propose that these deviations show mantle flow
260 deflected by the deep structures below the Paranapanema block, as we can
261 see in Figure 7. All the three main structures (Amazon and São Francisco
262 cratons and the Paranapanema block) seem to be diverting the flow in be-
263 tween them. Assumpção et al. [7] proposed that the anisotropy orientations
264 indicate flow around the keel of the São Francisco craton. Here, we add that
265 the Paranapanema block also deviates mantle flow.

266 The geometry of the Paranapanema block is not known in detail. Dif-
267 ferent geological and geophysical models have been proposed (Cordani [15],
268 Mantovani et al. [12], Milani and Ramos [16]). Different studies of surface
269 wave tomography tend to show large velocities beneath the northern part
270 of the Paraná basin, but with different geometries. The regional tomogra-
271 phy of Feng et al. [19] shows two high velocities in the northern part of the
272 Paraná basin and a separate high velocity keel in the southern part of the
273 São Francisco craton Figure 7-b. The proposal of Assumpção et al. [7] of
274 mantle flow around SFC was based on this keel. The global tomography
275 model SL2013svSchaeffer and Lebedev [20] Figure 7-a, on the other hand,
276 does not have resolution to separate these two keels.

277 We also observe different areas of large and small delays. Large delay
278 times are observed in the Pantanal basin and may indicate a strong astheno-

279 spheric channel, a more coherent flow, or a thicker asthenosphere. Further
280 to the northeast, large delays seem to predominate between the São Fran-
281 cisco ad Amazon cratons. Small delays are generally observed beneath areas
282 with thick lithosphere, such as the Amazon craton, and the Paranapanema
283 block. This may indicate thinner anisotropic asthenosphere, consistent with
284 the model of Hu et al. [27].

285 The SFC geometry used in the mantle flow calculation of Hu et al. [27],
286 did not significantly change the estimated SWS orientations. For this reason,
287 the model version used in Figure 6, Figure 5 and Figure 7 does not include
288 the SFC. We propose that the addition of a deep keel in southern part of
289 the SFC and the Paranapanema block should improve the fit to the observed
290 orientations.

Figure 5: a) Upper mantle flow directions and LPO directions, both at 200 km compared with the observed fast-polarization orientations. The yellow arrow is the absolute-plate motion (APM).

Figure 6: Histograms of the comparison of all station fast polarization orientation (ϕ) with the: a) absolute plate motion (APM) given by the HS3-NUVEL-1A model [17]; b) mantle flow orientations from the model of Hu et al. [27] at 200 km depth; c) LPO orientations from the model of [27] also at 200 km depth. Colored columns are more reliable values with measurements from 5 or more events, and white columns are all measurements.

Figure 7: Same as Figure 4, with bar colors showing the difference from the LPO model of Hu et al. [27]. SWS observations which deviate more than 10° clockwise from the LPO directions are plotted as red bars. Deviations more than 10° anticlockwise are shown as blue bars. Colors indicate S-wave velocity anomalies at 150 km depth from two different tomography models: a) SL2013Sv global model of Schaeffer and Lebedev [20], b) the regional model of Feng et al. [19].

291 5. Conclusions

292 In this work we present new measurements of shear wave splitting in the
293 Paraná and Pantanal basins, SE Brazil, in a area not well sampled before.
294 In general, considering the previous and new results in the continental mid-
295 plate South America, the fast polarization orientations have an average E-W
296 trend, previously related with the absolute plate motion directions (HS3-
297 NUVEL1A). Our results show that the subduction-induced, time dependent
298 flow model of Hu et al. [27] provides a much better explanation for the SWS
299 observations, which is seen using two proxies: convection velocity and LPO
300 at 200 km depth. The observed orientations are also consistent with the
301 flow around the Amazon craton, predicted by their model. We also support
302 the existence of a cratonic block under the Paraná basin, the Paranapanema
303 block, which diverts mantle flow. The small delay times observed in the
304 Paranapanema block seem to be typical of other cratonic areas.

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320 7. References

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